

Application of Accrual Based Accounting Problems at Central Aceh Government's

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Abstract: The present study has the objective to analyze the problems in the application of accrual-based accounting at the local government of the Central Aceh. This research is also aimed to find out the strategic steps carried out by the local government in handling the problems of application of accrual-based accounting - by means of conducting a case study at Central Aceh Regional Government. The method employed in this research was qualitative method with case study approach. The results demonstrated that the application of accrual-based accounting at the Central Aceh Regional Government has been supported by the presence of regulations (Qanun) of the Central Aceh Regency on the accounting policy and SAP (Standar Akuntansi Pemerintahan) procedural system at Central Aceh Regency; followed by the socialization at the beginning of this application, which is then supported by the information technology. What become the problem here the insufficient Human Resources (HR), either in terms of experience or educational backgrounds at the Office of Central Aceh Regional Financial Management. Subsequently, the Central Aceh Regional Government, via the Office of Central Aceh Regional Financial Management, took the strategic steps to overcome the problems in the application of accrual-based accounting through: (1) special training, (2) funding/ budgeted expenditures, and (3) supportive information technology and systems.

Keywords: Accrual problems, Strategic steps, Accrual basis

I. Introduction

Reform of the public sector in the 1980s occurred in the advanced industrial countries. Various changes were made, such as by adopting the approach of New Public Management (NPM) and Reinventing Government in many countries, especially the Anglo-Saxon countries (Sancoko, 2008). NPM is rooted in management theory which basically assumes that the commercial business practices and management of the private sector is better than the practice and management in the public sector. Therefore, to improve the performance of the public sector need to be adopted some practices and management techniques are applied in the private sector into the public sector (Mardiasmo, 2002). With the change in the public sector, there is also a change in the public sector accounting. Public sector accounting then follow and adjust to the changes that have occurred. As an example of a change in the accounting system of cash accounting into accrual accounting. Changes in accounting from cash basis into accrual basis is an important part of public sector reforms in Anglo-Saxon countries. The New Zealand government is considered the most advanced and successful in implementing accrual accounting has adopted the accounting system since 1991, as the first country in the world to adopt a system of accrual accounting, which is then followed by Japan, Italy and the other European countries although in Italian system is not effective.

Post-economic crisis that hit Indonesia in 1998, reforms in various fields to bring big changes, including in the field of public finance. One significant change is the change in accounting rule (Priyono, 2012). Changes in government accounting is very important because it is through the accounting process resulting financial information available to the various parties to be used in accordance with their respective goals. Before the era of public finance management reform in the recording system of accounting in the public sector are still using single entry. In the development of accounting system from cash basis transformed into accrual accounting.

Accrual accounting is an accounting basis where economic transactions and other events are recognized, recorded and presented in the financial statements at the time of the transaction, regardless of the time of cash or cash equivalents received or paid. In accrual accounting, time recording (recording) in accordance with the time of the flow of resources, so as to provide the most comprehensive information resource for the entire flow recorded. The positive impact of the adoption of accrual-based government accounting has been widely recognized by researchers. As a study conducted by Asfiansyah (2015), which states that the government accounting accrual significantly contribute in improving the quality of decision making for the efficiency and effectiveness of public expenditure through the financial information that is accurate and transparent, and improve the allocation of resources to inform the costs arising from a policy and transparency of the success of a program.

The paradigm change recording system at both central and local government began with the issuance of Law No. 1 of 2004 on perbendaharaan countries. Then the issuance of Government Regulation No. 71 of 2010 which requires each government entity to implement accrual-based accounting standards. Then Permendagri issuing regulations for local governments that Regulation No. 64 Year 2013 on Implementation of SAP Accrual Based on Local Government.

This study aims to analyze the problems in implementing accrual accounting in local government and to determine strategies undertaken Central Aceh Local Government in addressing the implementation of accrual based accounting.

The results of this study are expected to be useful for Local Government Central Aceh as inputs and sources of information on the implementation of accrual accounting, the problems faced and the solutions taken to overcome these problems. The results of this study are also expected to provide input in support of the implementation of PP 71 of 2010 and Regulation 64 Year 2013 on the application of accrual-based SAP in Local Government.

II. Literature Review

The area of financial accounting system is one subsystem organization that facilitates control by reporting the performance of local governments. The scope includes the area of financial accounting system accounting system policies, procedures accounting systems, human resources, and information technology. According Kepmendagri 29 of 2002 section 70 subsection (1) Regional Financial Accounting System is defined as "an accounting system that includes process recording, classification, interpretation, peringkasan transactions or financial events and financial reporting in the framework of implementation of the budget, implemented in the accounting principles generally acceptable".

Accrual basis in the Minister of the Interior No. 64 In 2013, Article 1 (10) explains that "the accrual basis of accounting is the basis which recognizes the effects of transactions and events during the transactions and events that occur, regardless of when cash or cash equivalents received or paid". Then Halim and Kusufi (2012) concludes that the accrual basis are able to meet the reporting objectives can not be met by the cash basis, which is the purpose of reporting the managerial and supervisory objectives.

Accrual basis or accrual basis is essentially an accounting method where receipts and expenses are recognized or recorded when the transaction occurs. Thus the recording in this method free from the influence of time when cash is received and when the expenditure is incurred. The important thing is that when a transaction occurs immediately noted, because it has implications for currency transactions into or out in the future. Transactions are recorded when they occur, even if the money has not actually received or released. Accrual basis used for the measurement of assets, liabilities and equity funds (Beechy, 2007).

Benefit accrual basis significantly felt in presenting information for all activities that occur. Sari and Son (2012) describes the reason for the application of the accrual basis to the public sector, including: (1) Accounting cash basis does not yield enough information, such as information on accounts payable and receivable for economic decision-making, so that the use of accrual basis is strongly recommended, (2) Only accrual accounting provides information that is appropriate to describe the cost of the actual operation, (3) Only accrual accounting can produce reliable information in the information assets and liabilities, and (4) Only accrual accounting generates information about the government's comprehensive financial.

Some of the challenges in the implementation of government accounting accrual (Blondal, 2003), namely: (1) Preparation of the culture change government entities, (2) The implementation model, (3) Requires communication, (4) Expertise accounting, and (5) Election Based system IT (information technology systems).

Indonesia is a developing country and the adoption of the accrual basis in the accounting system of the state government is not an easy thing, especially for developing countries. Following recommendation ADB (Asian Development Bank) adoption of the accrual basis for developing countries: (1) Precautions for selecting implementation strategies accrual basis, (2) The political commitment is one of the key, (3) The objective should be communicated, (4) the need for a reliable accountants, (5) should be sufficient accounting information system, (6) the supreme audit Agency should have the right resources, (7) the application of the accrual basis should be part of bureaucratic reform.

PP 71 of 2010 article 1, paragraph 8 states that the accrual-based government accounting standards is "government accounting standards that recognize the income, expenses, assets, debt, and equity in the accrual-based financial reporting, as well as recognizing the revenue, expenditure and financing in reporting implementation of the budget on the basis set out in the APBN / APBD ". Accrual basis of the balance sheet means that the assets, liabilities and equity are recognized and recorded at the transaction date, or when events or environmental conditions impact on government finances, regardless of when cash or cash equivalents received or paid.

Until the year 2013 budget, the local government is still implementing SAP based on Government Regulation No. 24 of 2005 concerning the Government Accounting Standards. Fundamental differences of Government Regulation No. 71 Year 2010 by Government Regulation No. 24 of 2005 is located at the base of the recording of transactions and types of financial reports.

The difference between the Government Accounting Standards Toward Cash Accrual (CTA) with the Government Accounting Standards accrual can be described in Table 1.

Table 1
Differences (Government Accounting Standards Toward Cash Accrual (GAS-TCA) and
The Government Accounting Standards Accrual (GAS-A)

Distinguishing	GAS-TCA	GAS-A
Types of Reports	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Budget Realization Reports; 2. Balance Sheet; 3. Cash Flow Statement; 4. Notes to Financial Statements. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Budget Realization Reports; 2. Balance Sheet; 3. Cash Flow Statement; 4. Notes to Financial Statements; 5. Operational Reports; 6. Report Changes to The Budget Balance More. 7. Statement of Changes in Equity
Revenue Recognition	When cash is received at the state/regional general cash account (except for the work unit of the agency general services.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Income-Operational Reports, when rights arise and/or the flow of economic resources; 2. Income- Budget Realization Reports, when cash is received.
Shopping Acknowledgment	When cash is issued.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Expense-Operational Reports, when liabilities arise, consumption of assets or decrease in economic benefits/service potential. 4. Shop at Budget Realization Reports, when payment cash out.

Sources: Yafie (2013)

Based on previous research on the application of accrual accounting for local governments there are still many problems in its implementation. Surepno (2015), on the Semarang city government has successfully implemented accrual accounting is supported by four main strategies, namely management commitment, regulatory development, information systems development and human resource development. However, the successful implementation of accrual accounting is still confronted with obstacles in its application, which is still limited Human Resources (HR), information technology support is not adequate, the problem of fixed assets and the lack of technical guidance for local governments (LGs).

Similarly, in the study Widianti, et al. (2016) found the issues of implementing accrual accounting in Tegal regency government, that the education level of the staff, finance staff training, quality and experience of information technology influence simultaneously on the implementation of accrual based accounting.

III. Methodology

This study used a qualitative method with case study approach. The case study is a research strategy where researchers investigated carefully inside a program, event, activity, process, or group of individuals. The cases are limited by time and activity, and researchers collected detailed information using a variety of data collection procedures based on a predetermined time (Creswell, 2013).

The case study chosen in this study because the case study has the advantages of case studies can lead researcher in the understanding of the issue or phenomenon or object that is complex and complicated. Then the researchers also benefited by gaining a broad and holistic knowledge about the strengths and weaknesses of previous research. The case studies highlighted in detail the contextual analysis of some of the events and conditions that limited and how the relationship between the two can be mutually influence (Yin, 2003).

Methods of data collection is the most strategic step in the study because the main goal of the research is to obtain data that can be accounted for then the validity level required sources and methods of data collection are credible.

According Sugiono (2010) there are several data collection techniques, including interviews and documentation. Interviews were conducted in person and depth (depth interview) to the informant involved and directly related to and do voice recording at the time of the interview. Informants in this study consisted of three people from the field of accounting, the Head of Division, section head and staff. Then two of the sub department of finance is the Head of sub department of finance and staff. The results are presented in the form of interview transcript of the interview which is then used as the data in the data processing. Then documentation as the source of the data used to complete the research, both in the form of written sources that provide information for the research process. Here's a list of participants who used informants in the study:

Table 2
Research Respondents

Identity of Informants	Position	Code
AM	Head of Accounting	KBA
EM	Head of Accounting & Reporting	KPA
KH	staff Reports	SPA
MD	Head of Finance	KKDPK
CH	Financial staff	SKDPK

Data analysis techniques in this study according to qualitative data analysis models Sugiyono (2010) after the collection of data: data reduction, data presentation and conclusion. Then to assure the validity of the data obtained, the researcher uses triangulation techniques. In this case the researchers compared data from interviews with documentation of data, and also compared the results of interviews with other interviews.

IV. Results

Problems Faced in Implementing Accrual Based Accounting in Central Aceh Local Government

Office of Financial Management Central Aceh district SKPD apart as well as SKPKD (Regional Finance Management Task Force), into a working unit of Central Aceh District Government are implementing and will be responsible for the implementation of accounting and financial reporting systems in Central Aceh District Government.

Accounting and reporting systems in Central Aceh which was initially based Toward Cash Accrual (CTA), with the publication of Regulation No. 64 of 2013, are required to turn into berbasis accrual accounting system. By changing the accounting system of Cash Toward Accrual (CTA) to accrual, is likely to encounter problems faced. The application of accrual accounting in government Kabupetn Central Aceh began in 2015, it is in accordance with Regulation No. 64 Year 2013, which provides the latest deadline for local governments throughout Indonesia to apply accrual accounting in 2015.

Challenge the application of accrual accounting in Central Aceh local government can be explained, (1) the Accounting and Information Technology (IT) based system, namely the unavailability of accounting systems and information technology systems were able to accommodate the requirements of the application of accrual accounting. This can be overcome Government of Central Aceh district by using the application of Management Information Systems Areas (SIMDA), (2) Commitment to Leadership, with the commitment and political support of leaders and decision-makers for the government, the strong support of the leadership is the key to the success of a change. It is indicated with the Qanun or decree of Central Aceh on policy and system of accrual accounting procedures, (3) Funding, in the implementation of accrual requires substantial funds and sufficient not only for the initial investment but also for the activities that are maintenance. This is due to the application of the accrual basis requires continuous updates so that the availability of funds maintenance also become absolute. Central Aceh District Government through the Office of Financial Management Central Aceh district has allocated a budget for the implementation of accrual accounting annually, and (4) Availability of Human Resources (HR) is competent. The financial statements are required to be arranged in an orderly and delivered by the local government to the Supreme Audit Agency (BPK) not later than three months after the fiscal year ends. The preparation and the preparation of financial statements requires adequate human resources in the control of government accounting. This is the problem in Central Aceh District Government, namely the lack of Human Resources (HR) competent good it is based on the educational background and experience. As explained in an interview Subsection Head of Finance Office of Financial Management Central Aceh District:

"This is a problem because we are right there that it's supposed to accrual should the accounting of its human resources are not you ... expected accounting education background" (KKDPK).

Central Aceh Local Government Strategic Steps in Addressing Issues Accrual Based Accounting Application

The emergence of problems in implementing accrual accounting, then there are several things to consider to achieve success (key succes factor) in the case of the application of the accrual basis. Even on these issues must also be taken strategic steps that need to be implemented to overcome these problems.

In Central Aceh district government through the Office of Financial Management Central Aceh district has several strategic steps in overcoming problems of implementation of accrual based accounting.

Training Tiered

Tiered shall include the leadership level up to the technical implementation of the policy, with the aim of socialization and training to improve skill execution, build awareness and encourage the involvement of all parties. The training was conducted for the first time that aktualnya based accounting training and then training the Regional Management Information System (SIMDA). This is consistent with an interview Head of Accounting and Reporting Financial Management Office of Central Aceh.

"There is ... no ... the first training for the implementation of accrual accounting that both applications SIMDA" (KPA).

Funding or Costs

In the framework of the implementation of the accrual, Central Aceh District Government requires substantial funds by considering the number of work units located in the region of Central Aceh and implement training required for various levels. Implementation of the accrual basis also require adequate funding, not only for the initial investment but also for the activities that are maintenance. This is due to the application of the accrual basis requires continuous updates so that the availability of funds maintenance also become absolute. Therefore, Central Aceh District Government through the Office of Financial Management Central Aceh district has allocated a budget for the implementation of accrual accounting annually in the form of activities contained in the DPA SKPD Office of Financial Management so that funding or cost is not an issue in practice. As noted Head of Finance stating that:

"Funding is already budgeted" (KBA) And supported the exposure of staff Accounting and Reporting: "It's been budgeted and sufficient ... It is already budgeted annually, in the form of activities in the DPA SKPD, so as to charge no problem" (SPA).

Adequate Information Technology

Changes in the accounting system in government entities are always accompanied by changes in information technology. In the implementation of the accrual basis, system information technology (IT) should also be updated to handle the extra information related to the accrual basis. The use of IT software can adopt the software used commercial company or government entity can design their own IT system to be applied existence of complexity of implementation of accrual accounting, it is certain that the adoption of accrual accounting in government accounting and IT systems need-based system is more complicated. To support the implementation of accrual accounting in Central Aceh district government, technology necessary information has been provided and supports the application of the Regional Management Information System (SIMDA) which is a software application provided by the Financial and Development Supervisory Agency (BPK). Regarding the availability of technology and information systems support, following the narrative of the Head of Accounting:

"... because we support coupled with SIMDA application developed by BPK" (KBA) The same response was also obtained from the Head of Finance staff interviews: "Very supportive and provided" (SKDPK).

V. Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion of research can be concluded, that the implementation of the application of accrual accounting in the Government of Central Aceh shows that the adoption of the new system in an entity is not easy, it requires a process that must be taken to change the existing system by making changes in some aspects. Then in observance encountered problems that the Human Resources (HR) is inadequate in terms of both experience and educational background of the Office of Financial Management Central Aceh district.

To overcome the problems faced, the Government of Central Aceh district through the Office of Financial Management Central Aceh district to take strategic steps to resolve the problem or obstacle implementation of accrual accounting, through: (1) special training, whether it is training that was conducted by BPK or by another body , (2) funding / costs already budgeted and sufficient for the implementation of accrual accounting, and (3) Technology and Information Systems that support and accommodate the adoption of the accrual basis. Applications used is SIMDA (Regional Management Information System), in which the application is granted by the BPK. Limitations of this study are only examine the problems that occur in the application of accrual accounting in the Office of Financial Management, doing research on several different SKPD in Central Aceh District Government. Suggestions for further research to conduct research in the scope of other local governments to expand the research results.

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